

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXXII. Adsorption of Coagulating ions in Presence of Non-electrolytes

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Adsorption of coagulating ions has been found to be higher with the ions of lower valency and *vice versa*. In presence of small quantities of non-electrolytes (dioxane, *n*-propanol), the adsorption increases and with methanol at the same concentrations of non-electrolytes, it always decreases, irrespective of their nature. The observations have been explained on the basis of the predominant role played by (i) decrease in electronic charge of colloid particles or (ii) the decrease in the activity coefficient of coagulating ions when non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant are added.

According to Freundlich¹ and Weiser² the ions, which are more readily adsorbed, will coagulate a sol at a lower concentration of the electrolyte and *vice versa*. Cations of different valencies are also believed to be equally adsorbed from equimolar solutions. Sen³ has reported an increase in the adsorption of ions in presence of sugar. Yadava and Chatterji⁴ have also obtained results, which are in agreement with the observations of Mukherjee *et al.*⁵ Ostwald⁶ has pointed out that the 'density of the charge instead of magnitude of the charge' and the 'compression of the double layer' may be responsible for the coagulation of colloids; but these are not of sufficient significance. Yadava's⁷ observation of a slight lowering in the adsorption, when methanol is added to As_2S_3 and Fe_2O_3 sols, may explain the sensitisation observed by Chaudhury⁸. The phenomena of sensitisation and protection have been ascribed by Freundlich and Loring⁹ to the presence of colloidal ions in the lyophilic sols and absorption of non-electrolytes on the surface of colloidal particles. Pauli and Kitaj¹⁰ explained sensitisation on the basis of an exchange taking place between the oppositely charged groups of hydrophobic and hydrophilic colloids.

Several investigators¹¹ have found As_2S_3 sol to be stabilised by addition of urea and glycol, both increasing the dielectric constant of water. Mirnik and Tezak¹² made

1. *Kolloid Z.*, 1907, 1, 321.
2. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 955.
3. *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 310.
4. *This Journal*, 1943, 20, 25.
5. *Ibid.*, 1928, 5, 704.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 981.
7. *This Journal*, 1943, 20, 110.
8. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1481.
9. Kaiser Wilhelm Gesellschaftes Festschrift, p. 82, 1921.
10. *Kolloid Z.*, 1938, 82, 43.
11. Kaeser, *Biochem. Z.*, 1925, 157, 106.
12. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 65.

adsorption measurements of AgCl sol and showed that the effect of coagulation by neutral electrolytes lowered the adsorption capacity. In stable region, the adsorption capacities are relatively high, but in unstable region, low. Adsorption studies of thorium ion on positive and negative halides and silver thiocyanate sols¹³ have shown that adsorption increases with positive sol on increasing the stabilising Ag^+ ions. For negative sols, where more adsorption is expected, it is much lower than the positive sol with the same amount of the solid phase and the same concentration of stabilising ions. Negative sols showed no adsorption in presence of Na_2SO_4 . An attempt has been made here to explain the effect of different non-electrolytes of varying dielectric constants on the adsorption of coagulating ions of increasing valencies.

EXPERIMENTAL

The adsorption of mono-, di-, and tri-valent coagulating ions, viz., iodate, sulphate, and ferricyanide, was studied at their coagulating concentrations during 1 hr. The concentration of each electrolyte in the coagulating mixture was always kept constant, irrespective of their volume and nature of the non-electrolyte present in the coagulating system. For the estimation of adsorbed sulphate ions, chromium hydroxide sol was taken in a stoppered bottle (250 ml) and $N/20\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution (10.6 ml) was taken in a similar bottle along with the requisite volume of distilled water to make the coagulating electrolyte mixture 50 ml. After a thorough mixing of the contents of the two bottles, the sol-electrolyte mixture was kept for 1 hr. and then filtered. The unadsorbed sulphate ions were determined gravimetrically as BaSO_4 . The physical and chemical adsorption of the precipitating ions were determined as follows.

Chromium hydroxide sol (50 ml) was taken in two separate stoppered bottles (250 ml). The sol in one was coagulated by adding minimum amount of H_2SO_4 and the coagulum was washed with water till free of the electrolyte. This coagulum was suspended in distilled water (50 ml) and was replaced in the container. Now to both these bottles, one containing the sol and the other containing the coagulum, was added $N/20\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution (10.6 ml) and made to 50 ml with distilled water. After thorough mixing the bottles were left for 1 hr., contents filtered separately, and the adsorbed sulphate ions determined as BaSO_4 . The adsorption with the sol comprises both physical and chemical adsorption and that of the sulphate in the bottle containing coagulum-electrolyte mixture, only physical adsorption, the difference between the two indicating the chemical adsorption. A similar procedure was adopted for determining the physical and chemical adsorption in the case of iodate and ferricyanide volumetrically. The adsorption of iodate and ferricyanide was determined iodometrically, both in presence and absence of non-electrolytes, such as *n*-propanol, dioxane, and methanol at their five concentrations. In the estimation of iodate and ferricyanide ions in presence of dioxane, as the medium was found to react with sodium thiosulphate during titrations, due precaution was taken in calculating their adsorption. The adsorption of each ion has been calculated in terms of equivalents of anions adsorbed per g. of sol.

13. Sen *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 313; 1925, 29, 435.

TABLE I

Adsorption of iodate and sulphate ions.

Cr(OH)₃ sol=8.104 g./litre. *N*/3-KIO₃ (9.8 ml) or *N*/20-K₂SO₄ (10.6 ml) + 50 ml sol + non-electrolyte + water. Total volume=100 ml.

Non-electrolyte.	Adsorption of iodate.				Adsorption of sulphate.			
	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	*[IO ₃] ⁻ × 10 ⁻³ .	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	*[SO ₄ ⁼] × 10 ³ .
Dioxane.								
0 ml	0.1630 g.	0.0046 g.	0.1584 g.	2.24	0.0432 g.	0.0038 g.	0.0395 g.	2.02
5	0.1600	0.0046	0.1614	2.28	0.0460	0.0038	0.0422	2.17
10	0.1626	0.0046	0.1580	2.23	0.0442	0.0038	0.0404	2.08
15	0.1600	0.0046	0.1554	2.19	0.0430	0.0038	0.0392	2.01
20	0.1578	0.0046	0.1532	2.16	0.0418	0.0038	0.0380	1.95
25	0.1560	0.0040	0.1514	2.14	0.0402	0.0038	0.0364	1.87
<i>n</i> -Propanol.								
5	0.1640	0.0046	0.1594	2.25	0.0446	0.0038	0.0408	2.09
10	0.1618	0.0046	0.1572	2.22	0.0436	0.0038	0.0398	2.05
15	0.1598	0.0046	0.1552	2.19	0.0424	0.0038	0.0386	1.98
20	0.1576	0.0046	0.1530	2.16	0.0410	0.0038	0.3720	1.91
25	0.1550	0.0046	0.1504	2.12	0.0400	0.0038	0.0362	1.86
Methanol.								
5	0.1608	0.0046	0.1562	2.20	0.0428	0.0038	0.0390	2.00
10	0.1582	0.1536	0.1536	2.17	0.0412	0.0038	0.0374	1.92
15	0.1562	0.0046	0.1516	2.14	0.0398	0.0038	0.0360	1.85
20	0.1538	0.0046	0.1492	2.11	0.0382	0.0038	0.0344	1.78
25	0.1520	0.0046	0.1474	2.08	0.0378	0.0038	0.0340	1.74

TABLE II

Adsorption of ferricyanide ions.

Electrolyte=12.4 ml of *N*/50-potassium ferricyanide. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Volume of non-electrolyte.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	*1/3[Ferricyanide] × 10 ³ .
Dioxane.				
0 ml	0.0550 g.	0.0034 g.	0.0516 g.	1.80
5	0.0570	0.0034	0.0536	1.87
10	0.0558	0.0034	0.0524	1.83
15	0.0546	0.0034	0.0512	1.78
20	0.0538	0.0034	0.0504	1.76
25	0.0528	0.0034	0.0492	1.72

*Equiv. of anion adsorbed in g./g. sol.

TABLE II (contd.)

Volume of non-electrolyte.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	$1/3$ [Ferricyanide] $\times 10^3$.
		n-Propanol.		
5	0.0558 g.	0.0034 g.	0.0524 g.	1.83
10	0.0542	0.0034	0.0508	1.77
15	0.0530	0.0034	0.0496	1.73
20	0.0518	0.0034	0.0484	1.69
25	0.0508	0.0034	0.0474	1.65
		Methanol.		
5	0.0552	0.0034	0.0508	1.77
10	0.0530	0.0034	0.0496	1.73
15	0.0518	0.0034	0.0484	1.69
20	0.0508	0.0034	0.0474	1.65
25	0.0500	0.0034	0.0466	1.63

DISCUSSION

On examining the adsorption data of coagulating ions in absence of non-electrolytes, it is found that 2.24×10^{-3} g. equiv. of iodate ions per g. of sol are adsorbed, which is maximum as compared to sulphate and ferricyanide ions, i.e. 2.02×10^{-3} and 1.80×10^{-3} g. equiv./g. of sol respectively. This confirms the earlier observations made by Sen *et al.*¹³ and Gann¹⁴, who have shown that the adsorption of coagulating ions decreases with their increasing valency. According to Verwey and Overbeek¹⁵, the energy of interaction between two approaching particles is composed of long range van der Waals attraction. For a given colloid, the attraction is assumed to be constant, whereas repulsion changes with electrolyte content of the system. Due to the faster neutralisation of charge of colloid particles by multivalent coagulating ions, the stability of sol decreases, and so the adsorption.

The influence of non-electrolytes on the stability of sol is a confused problem and therefore three non-electrolytes, such as dioxane ($D=2$), *n*-propanol ($D=20$), and methanol ($D=35$), have been selected to explain the role of dielectric constant in adsorption phenomenon. On adding small quantities (5 ml) of these non-electrolytes to the sol in presence of each coagulating electrolyte, the adsorption of coagulating ions increases in presence of dioxane and *n*-propanol, but decreases in methanol. At higher concentrations of all non-electrolytes, the amount of adsorbed coagulating ions always decreases. Mirnik and Tezak¹², during the coagulation of AgCl sol with electrolytes of varying valencies, observed that the adsorption was high in stable region and *vice versa*. The stability of a sol in presence of non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant depends on the combined effect of two opposing factors, namely, decrease in electric charge of colloid particles and decrease in activity coefficient of coagulating ions. The increase in adsorption in presence of 5 ml of dioxane and *n*-propanol is due to stabilisation of the sol, followed by greater

12. *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1916, 3, 66.

15. "Theory of Stability of Colloids", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1948.

decrease in the activity coefficient of coagulating ions and to a lesser extent, the decrease in charge of colloidal particles. The decrease in adsorption in presence of methanol may be attributed to the predominant role played by the decrease in electronic charge of the sol particles. One of the authors⁷ has already shown that charge on colloidal particles decreases on adding the increasing volume of non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant. The results obtained in the present investigation also confirm the above finding.

In presence of equal volumes of non-electrolytes, the adsorption is greatest in dioxane, less in *n*-propanol, and least in methanol. Had there been only one factor, *i.e.*, the decrease in electronic charge of colloid particles responsible, the results would have been just the reverse. But the observation reveals that there is also another factor known as "decrease in activity coefficient of coagulating ions", which also plays a very important role in determining the nature of adsorption. The activity coefficient of coagulating ions is greatly diminished in presence of dioxane having lowest dielectric constant, whereas the decrease is minimum in presence of methanol of higher dielectric constant, and this confirms adsorption values.

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